

Evaluating SDG Network Models: A Network Science Ontology-Based Framework: Literature Scoping Review

Objective

The aim for this literature scoping review is to investigate how academic journal papers have described how network science and its analysis methods are applied to the interrelations between the UN 2030 Agenda Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) and associated targets and indicators.

Aspects such as the contribution of different types of networks (e.g., actor networks, transport and energy) or the analysis of a single Sustainable Development Goals are to be excluded from the review.

Review question and framework

The research question to be investigated in the context of the review is:

“How are network science and network analysis methods applied to the interlinkages between Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and their targets and indicators?”

The Population, Concepts and Context framework was applied to the review question producing the following table identifying its key terms, related expressions and non-relevant (to be excluded) expressions.

	Key terms	Related expressions	Non-relevant (to be excluded) expressions
Population	Sustainable Development Goal*	SDG*, "Sustainable Development Target*", Sustainable Development Indicator*, UN 2030	
Concepts	Network Science	network analysis, complex networks	neural network, Bayesian Network, AI, artificial intelligence, ML, Machine Learning
Context	Interlinkages between SDGs, targets and indicators		

Eligibility Criteria and Information Sources

Given the review realm and with the aim of restricting the review to commonly accepted academic publication standards, only journal articles and reviews listed in Elsevier's Scopus and Clarivate's Web of Science databases are considered for electronic search.

Given the publication date of the UN 2030 Agenda Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) only publications after 2016 are considered.

Only reports written in English are considered.

Search strategy

Scopus (last applied circa November 2025)

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY ( ( SDG* OR "Sustainable Development Goal*" OR "Sustainable Development Target*" OR
OR "Sustainable Development Indicator*" )
AND ( "network analysis" OR "network science" OR "complex networks" )
ANDNOT ( "neural network" OR "Bayesian Network" OR AI OR "artificial intelligence" OR ML OR "Machine
Learning" ) )
AND ( LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "ar" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "re" ))
AND ( LIMIT-TO ( LANGUAGE , "English" ) )
AND PUBYEAR > 2016
```

Web of Science (last applied circa November 2025)

```
ALL=("sustainable development goal*" OR SDG* OR "UN2030" OR "Sustainable Development Target*" OR
"Sustainable Development Indicator*")
AND ALL=("network analysis*" OR "network science" OR "complex network*")
NOT ALL = ("neural network" OR "Bayesian Network" OR AI OR "Artificial Intelligence" OR ML OR
"Machine Learning")
AND DT=(ARTICLE OR REVIEW)
AND LA=(ENGLISH)
AND PY=(2017-2025)
```

Record and Report screening process

Reason	Description
A. SDG framing, no SDG network	SDGs are mentioned narratively or conceptually, but there is no formal SDG–network representation , i.e., SDGs, targets or indicators are not the focus of the paper (e.g., only the relation or impact in the SDGs are described, other types of networks are described)
B. Bipartite / governance networks	The network relates actors, firms, initiatives, cities to SDGs, with SDGs goals, targets and indicators treated as labels , not interacting nodes
C. Case-level indicator replications	Local/sectoral SDG indicator networks that mimic SDG relations but do not address the SDG goals, targets or indicators
D. Nexus/system models without SDG network formalization	Network models interactions among domain variables (e.g., water-energy-food), referencing SDGs but not constructing SDG–SDG edges
E. Non-SDG paper	The record was identified through search noise but does not analyze SDGs, i.e., record topic is totally off the review objective realm. (e.g., other entities using the SDG acronym)

From the 495 unique records found in the database query, 58 reports were considered for screening, yielding 9 reports to be included in the review. To these, 16 additional reports found in citation search or suggested by experts were added.

PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for new systematic reviews which included searches of databases, registers and other sources

Source: Page MJ, et al. BMJ 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71.

This work is licensed under CC BY 4.0. To view a copy of this license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>